

STUDY OF THE ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY OF THE SUPRAMOLECULAR COMPLEX OF GLYCYRRHIZIC ACID AND RUTIN

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In leading pharmaceutical companies, the development of new herbal medicines and their application in medical practice has significantly increased. Medicinal plants are of great importance in the global healthcare system due to the effective therapeutic properties of their biologically active components. Currently, phenolic compounds isolated from plants show antioxidant, antihypoxic, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, and vasodilatory activities. Among the most studied phenolic compounds are the flavonoids rutin and quercetin. The main mechanism of flavonoid action is their high antioxidant capacity, which provides a wide range of biological effects. However, due to their low solubility, the study of their biological activity is limited. At present, many research centers worldwide are conducting studies aimed at increasing the solubility of drugs (nanopharmacology). To this end, approaches such as nanoparticles, nanocapsules, nanoemulsions, gelatin-based formulations, and complexes with cyclodextrins and phospholipids have been proposed. In this regard, supramolecular complexes also play an important role.

The experiments were performed on a model of acute exudative inflammation induced by carrageenan (a classical phlogogen) via subplantar injection. The study was conducted on male rats weighing 180 ± 20 g. Aqueous solutions of rutin and glycyrrhizic acid/rutin (GA/Rutin) complexes were administered intragastrically at doses of 20–40 mg/kg. One hour later, 0.1 ml of a 1% carrageenan solution was injected into the aponeurosis of the hind paw. Before carrageenan injection, the initial paw volumes were measured. The anti-inflammatory effect was assessed 3 and 24 hours after inflammation induction. Edema was determined as the difference between inflamed and non-inflamed paw volumes. The anti-exudative effect (AEE) was calculated as the reduction of edema compared to control animals.

In the carrageenan-induced inflammation model, maximal edema in control rats was observed 3 hours after injection, when paw volume increased by $93.8 \pm 4.6\%$ compared to baseline, and decreased to $50.0 \pm 6.5\%$ after 24 hours. Similar dynamics were observed in the rutin- and GA/Rutin-treated groups, but with significantly reduced edema. Rutin at doses of 20 and 40 mg/kg reduced paw swelling 3 hours after carrageenan injection to $65.1 \pm 17.0\%$ and $53.3 \pm 14.3\%$ ($p < 0.05$), and after 24 hours to $17.4 \pm 3.75\%$ and $22.4 \pm 2.47\%$ ($p < 0.01$), respectively. The calculated AEE values for rutin were 31.0% and 65.2% (20 mg/kg) and 43.0% and 55.2% (40 mg/kg) at 3 and 24 hours, respectively. In the GA/Rutin-treated groups, paw edema at doses of 20 and 40 mg/kg was $44.1 \pm 6.8\%$ and $26.3 \pm 4.07\%$ after 3 hours, and $12.8 \pm 2.75\%$ and $20.5 \pm 6.82\%$ after 24 hours, respectively, all significantly lower compared to controls. The AEE values for GA/Rutin were 53.0% and 74.4% (20 mg/kg) and 72.0% and 59.0% (40 mg/kg) at 3 and 24 hours, respectively.

The obtained results show that under inflammatory conditions, the GA/Rutin supramolecular complex demonstrates stronger anti-exudative activity compared to rutin alone at the studied doses (20–40 mg/kg)